

COMPARISON OF CARTILAGE ISLAND AND TEMPORALIS FASCIA GRAFTS IN MYRINGOPLASTY: GRAFT UPTAKE AND HEARING RESULTS

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Abstract

Objectives: To compare the hearing outcome and graft success in patients undergoing temporal muscle fascia versus cartilage island graft myringoplasty.

Study Design: Prospective cohort study.

Study Place and Duration: Combined Military Hospital, ENT Department, Rawalpindi, Pakistan between June-2024 and June-2025.

Methodology: A total of 190 patients who underwent myringoplasty were included and divided into Group-TMF and Group-CI based on type of graft used. Hearing outcome and success of graft was assessed in both the groups. Intergroup comparison of hearing outcome and success of graft was done using Mann Whittney U-test and Chi-square test, respectively.

Results: A total of 190 patients divided into two groups were included. Median age was 36.00 (18.25) years. There were 117 (61.60%) male and 73 (38.40%) female patients. In Group-TMF, median pre-grafting ABG was 29.00 (3.00) dB while in Group-CI, it was 29.00 (10.00) dB, ($p = 0.918$). In Group-TMF, median six months post-grafting ABG was 16.00 (3.00) dB while in Group-CI, it was 10.00 (5.00) dB, ($p < 0.001$). Frequency of graft success in Group-TMF ($n = 95$) was 75 (78.95%) while it was 87 (91.58%) in Group-CI ($n = 95$), ($p = 0.014$).

Conclusion: Cartilage island graft provides higher graft success as well as hearing outcome in patients who underwent myringoplasty in comparison to temporal muscle fascia graft.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) is one of the common ear pathologies encountered at healthcare settings which can lead to perforation of the tympanic membrane (TM).^{1, 2} This infectious condition of ear has been reported to have a global annual incidence of 31 million people and a prevalence of 300 million.^{3, 4} The primary pathophysiological mechanism that leads to the perforation of TM is driven by chronic inflammatory process which leads to production of inflammatory fluid which damages and weakens

the TM proceeding to its perforation.⁵ This disease is not just common but also a highly common and preventable cause of hearing loss.⁶ Once TM perforates secondary to CSOM, first step to ensure conductance of myringoplasty is to determine that the ear ossicles are not disrupted.⁷ Primary goal of this surgical procedure is to improve the ability of hearing of the ailing patients and this is achieved by closing the air-bone gap (ABG) and improving the bone and air conduction (BC and AC).⁸ Outcomes of this procedure is impacted by several factors including

patient’s gender, age, nature of defect, positive smoking history and presence of comorbidities.⁹ Another factor that is hypothesized to influence the procedural outcomes is the nature of graft. In this instance, a study reported that the frequency of graft success with temporal muscle fascia (TMF) graft was 80.2% while with cartilage island (CI) graft, it was 93.8%.¹⁰

When it comes to comparison of TMF and CI grafts outcomes, not much evidence is available, particularly at regional level. In addition, no single type of graft material has been established as the best material for this purpose. Therefore, present study was conducted to compare the hearing outcome and graft success in patients undergoing TMF versus CI graft myringoplasty.

METHODOLOGY

This prospective cohort study spanned from June-2024 to June-2025 and took place at Combined Military Hospital, ENT Department, Rawalpindi, Pakistan after the proposal was approved by ethical

review board of the institution (Ref no.: 994; dated: 3rd May 2024).

Inclusion criteria: Male and female patients who were age 18 years or above and underwent myringoplasty for Chronic Otitis Media related Tympanic membrane perforation were included.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with prior history of such procedure, sensorineural type of hearing loss, comorbid conditions that may influence wound healing/graft uptake like diabetes, steroid use or active malignancy, disruption of the chain of ear ossicles and those with active infection of the ear to be operated were excluded.

A sample size of 190 patients (95 in each group) was calculated based on 5% level of significance, power of 80% and anticipated frequency of graft success of TMF and CI graft myringoplasty of 80.2% and 93.8%, respectively.¹⁰ This calculation was done using WHO sample size calculator software which was based on following formula:

$$n = \frac{\left\{ z_{1-\alpha/2} \sqrt{2\bar{P}(1-\bar{P})} + z_{1-\beta} \sqrt{P_1(1-P_1) + P_2(1-P_2)} \right\}^2}{(P_1 - P_2)^2}$$

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Sample selection technique was consecutive, non-probability sampling.

Once the purpose of study was comprehensively explained to the patients, they were presented with a written consent form which they had to sign for becoming part of the study. After that baseline characteristics including age, gender, laterality of disease and pre-procedural ABG were documented. Assessment of ABG was performed using pure-tone audiometry (PTA). For pre-operative ABG assessment, it was made sure that it was performed not more than seven days before the surgery. Operative technique chosen for myringoplasty was chosen to be endoscopic.

Based on the type of graft material being used, patients were divided into two groups. Patients who received TMF graft for myringoplasty were placed in Group-TMF while those who received CI graft were placed in Group-CI. To avoid any bias related to the pre-surgical, intra-surgical and post-

surgical factors, it was made sure that all the patients received similar pre-surgical care package as per institutional protocols, that all surgeries were performed by the consultant ENT surgeons with a minimum of three years of experience post-fellowship and ensuring provision of uniform post-surgical surgical care package as per institutional protocols to all the patients. After surgery, patients were asked to follow up on monthly basis till the completion of six months. At six months follow up visit, graft success and post-procedural ABG was assessed through PTA. Analysis of the collected data was performed by inputting data in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. Based on Shapiro-Wilk test, it was found that quantitative variables (age and ABG) were not normally distributed for which these were represented as median interquartile range (IQR) and inter-group comparative analysis was done by using Mann

Whitney U-test. Qualitative variables (gender, disease laterality and graft success) representation was done as percentage and frequency, and intergroup comparative analysis was done using Chi-square test. Pre- and post-grafting ABG comparison was performed using Wilcoxon matched-pair signed rank test was used. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 190 patients were included. Median age was 36.00 (18.25) years. There were 117 (61.60%) male and 73 (38.40%) female patients. Left sided perforation was observed in 97 (51.10%) and right sided perforation was observed in 93 (48.90%) patients. Intergroup comparative analysis of baseline characteristics is given in Table-I:

Table-I: Intergroup comparative analysis of baseline characteristics (n = 190)

Characteristic	Group-TMF (n = 95)	Group-CI (n = 95)	p-value
Age (Median IQR)	36.00 (20.00) years	36.00 (15.90) years	0.622 ^a
Gender			
Male	58 (61.05%)	59 (62.11%)	0.881 ^b
Female	37 (38.95%)	36 (37.89%)	
Laterality			
Left	49 (51.58%)	48 (50.53%)	0.885 ^b
Right	46 (48.42%)	47 (49.47%)	

IQR – Interquartile range, TMF = Temporal muscle fascia, CI = Cartilage Island, a = Mann Whitney U-test, b = Chi-square test

In Group-TMF, median pre-grafting ABG was 29.00 (3.00) dB while in Group-CI, it was 29.00 (10.00) dB, (p = 0.918). In Group-TMF, median six months post-grafting ABG was 16.00 (3.00) dB

while in Group-CI, it was 10.00 (5.00) dB, (p < 0.001). Intragroup and intergroup comparison of hearing parameters before and after procedure is given in Table-II:

Table-II: Intragroup and intergroup comparison of ABG before and six months after procedure (n = 190)

Parameter	Group-TMF (n = 95)	Group-CI (n = 95)	p-value
Median pre-procedural ABG	29.00 (3.00) dB	29.00 (10.00) dB	0.918 ^a
Median post-procedural ABG	16.00 (3.00) dB	10.00 (5.00) dB	< 0.001 ^a
p-value	< 0.001 ^c	< 0.001 ^c	

ABG = Air-bone gap, TMF = Temporal muscle fascia, CI = Cartilage Island, a = Mann Whitney U-test, c = Wilcoxon matched-pair signed rank test

Frequency of graft success in Group-TMF (n = 95) was 75 (78.95%) while it was 87 (91.58%) in Group-CI (n = 95), (p = 0.014). Intergroup

comparison of frequency of graft success is given in Table-III:

Table-III: Intergroup comparison of frequency of graft success (n = 190)

	Group-TMF (n = 95)	Group-CI (n = 95)	p-value
Graft success	75 (78.95%)	87 (91.58%)	0.014 ^b

TMF = Temporal muscle fascia, CI = Cartilage Island, b = Chi-square test

DISCUSSION

Present study focused on comparing two different types of graft materials, i.e., TMF and CI which are used to replace perforated TM in patients having

CSOM. Primary reason for this comparison was to find a graft material among fascia and cartilage that can provide best hearing outcomes since hearing impairment is directly related to poor

quality of life (QOL).^{11,12} Effective management of hearing impairment secondary to TM perforation is thus of utmost importance to improve patient's QOL.

In this study, a clear male predominance was observed upon analysis of distribution of CSOM and TM perforation across genders with males constituting __% of the study population. A study reported similar trend of gender distribution of this ear condition showing male predominance with males making up 53.7% of the sufferers.¹⁵ In another study, it was found that male to female ratio in CSOM cases was 1.09 indicating a male predominance in this regard.¹⁶ The differences in the bacterial infection susceptibility, hygienic practices and environmental exposures may be the cause of this male predominance but evidence regarding causal relationship between gender and this ear condition has not been established.¹⁷

Upon analyzing the laterality of the disease, there was a slightly higher frequency of disease affecting left rather than the right ear with left ear involvement being observed in __% of the patients. Similar to this finding, a study demonstrated various characteristics of patients with TM perforation and reported that left ear was affected in 56.2% of the patients while right ear was involved in 43.8% patients.¹⁸ In another study, it was reported that frequency of left ear being diseased was 58.9% which was similar to present study.¹⁹ The reason for this left ear predominance is yet unknown in literature.

Upon analysis of the hearing outcomes, it was found that median ABG was significantly lower in patients who received CI graft as compared to TMF graft ($p < 0.001$). Contrary to this, a study found that this closure of ABG was significantly higher with TMF graft rather than the cartilage graft ($p = 0.036$).²⁰ In another study, it was found that when TMF and CI grafts were compared, non-significant difference was observed between the two types ($p = 0.29$).¹⁰ In another study, non-significant difference was observed between the two types of graft in terms of post-grafting ABG ($p = 0.765$).²¹ Reason for this difference could not be determined but this finding was unique as compared to previous literature.

Similarly, upon comparative analysis of graft success, it was found that the frequency of graft success is significantly higher with CI rather than TMF graft ($p = 0.014$). Similar to this, a study reported that success rate was significantly higher with CI rather than TMF graft ($p = 0.048$).¹⁰ In another study, when graft success rates were compared between fascia and cartilage grafts, it was found that with cartilage, success rate was significantly higher in comparison to TMF graft (92% versus 84%, $p = 0.029$).²⁰ Similarly, another study exhibited significantly higher success rate with cartilage rather than fascia graft ($p = 0.01$).²² Contrarily, one study found that in regards to graft success after six months of grafting, no significant difference was observed upon comparison of fascia and cartilage TM grafts ($p = 0.362$).²³ The exact cause for difference could not be determined but it is hypothesized that this may have been caused by difference in operative conditions, surgeon expertise, post-procedural care protocols, study conditions and patient demographics of different studies and present study.

Given the findings of this research, CI graft is recommended to be used as preferred graft material rather than the TMF as it provides significantly better hearing outcomes as well as higher graft uptake success rate. Lack of long term follow up was the only limitation of present study.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, cartilage island graft is a better graft material choice since it not only provides significantly higher graft success rate but also results in significantly greater closing of the air-bone gap in comparison to temporal muscle fascia graft.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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None

Author's Contribution

Rahat Kalsoom: Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data and manuscript drafting

Naeem Riaz Bhalli: Manuscript drafting and reviewing, final approval

Irfan Saeed: Substantial contributions to acquisition of data

Faiqa Batool: Substantial contributions to acquisition of data

Tahir Liaquat: Substantial contributions to analysis and interpretation of data

Liaquat Ali: Critical review

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